

ISic3653

I.Sicily inscription 3653

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.10.31 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Monte Alburnia di Gangi

Provenance

'nella zona di M. Alburnia', which is

<http://pleiades.stoa.org/places/462327>

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Gangi, Museo Civico di
Gangi

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 199-200 no.2 tav.71.1

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